

THE CONCEPT OF THE FAMILY AND THE SYSTEM OF PUBLIC RELATIONS IN THE FAMILY

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Annotation: The article describes the importance of education in the prevention of family crises, the problems of family education in the formation of certain physical, mental, moral and spiritual qualities in a person and the psychological features of their elimination.

Key words: family, social education, ethics, education, aesthetics, environment, psychological features, person, personality, tradition.

Today, the process of changing the form of such dangerous traditions as divorce¹, an increase in the number of single-parent families, a decrease in educational attitudes, a deterioration in the quality of family relations and satisfaction with marriage, and a decrease in the adaptive capabilities of men and women are observed. If in the recent past, marriage was considered in most cases as an indestructible, strong life union, today divorce is becoming a common and fairly common form of resolving family disputes, as a result of which many couples dissolve the marriage, refusing it comprehensively. and objectively solve problematic situations aimed at violation. In addition, as proven by life experience and international scientific research, in most cases it is a strong and psychological correction of the development of various accentuations (accentuation, focus), which increase the disruption of family activities, divorces, primarily emotional disorders in girls, constant mental stress becomes severe. factor.

These cases require special attention and strengthening of special studies of the institute of the modern family in women in the first years of marriage. Strengthening the family, of course, often depends on its socio-economic, legal protection. In addition, an important, and in most cases the main reason for the problems that arise is that girls are not suitable for family life individual-spiritual characteristics, low level of their readiness for the necessary interactions, insufficient adaptive potential. In this regard, one of the topical areas for the prevention of stagnant marriage, its proper functioning, as well as ensuring the mental health of girls is the development of effective features of their adaptation to family life.

Family life is one of the most important aspects of human life. For the same reason, the attitude of society to laws and rules is also expressed in various interpersonal problems, communication, exchange of ideas, discussions in the family, so educating young people in the spirit of patriotism will help the family to be strong and noble. feelings of character in parental relationships, high dependence on the formation of spiritual feelings. Parents and adults in the family are entrusted with the high and responsible task of educating the younger generation to be a perfect person in the family.

In our country, the family is always protected by the state and is revered as the highest value. Since the family is the main and important center of socialization, its role in the beliefs and worldview of young people brought up in this environment is significant. The opening of the research institute "Mahalla va oila" in our republic has become an important event aimed at increasing the role and responsibility of the family in educating young people in society. From this point of view, education can be defined as the process of forming a person's idea of himself and his qualities. Therefore, the more clearly and correctly each person knows and imagines himself, the less likely that he will act against the norms of society, that is, he will be brought up. The process of self-awareness and assessment of existing qualities is often difficult for a particular person, that is, the nature of a person is such that he does not correspond to the norms of that society, tries not to understand unpleasant qualities, "hides" them, even such ideas and knowledge are relegated to the unconscious. (According to the theory of the Austrian scientist Z. Freud). This is not a deliberate action, this is a unique defense mechanism of each person. Such a protective mechanism often protects a person from various bad complications and emotional experiences. But it should be emphasized that the positive or negative image of the "I" is influenced by the external environment that surrounds this person environment, others and their attitudes play a big role. The person looks at others and imagines himself as if he sees himself in a mirror. This process in psychology is called reflection.

Unfortunately, family conflicts are a hot topic in today's society. Every family faces difficult situations in their life. Their solution is carried out in conditions of conflicting individual needs, motives, interests. Family disputes are divided into: spouses, parents, children, parents of spouses, grandparents, grandchildren. The main role in family relations is occupied by disputes in marriage [4]. External factors have a significant impact on the occurrence of conflicts in marriage. The financial situation of many families is deteriorating, one or both spouses are overloaded with work, one of them does not work normally, one of them is away from home for a long time, there is no opportunity to place children in child care institutions or other institutions, etc. One of the most common problems in everyday life There may be conflicts between parents and children. The child often experiences peer pressure about the absence of an older brother from the parents. This affects his neuroscopic state. This means that the number of teenagers with deviant behavior is increasing, and crime is growing. When resolving a family dispute, you should not avoid problems, but solve them. It is necessary to communicate constructively and calmly with the goal of a solution, not victory or protection. The involvement of third parties in the dispute is not recommended, as they can lead to an aggravation of major names.

As we have already mentioned, the crisis is not only a bad relationship between spouses. A crisis is a situation that requires changes, new decisions and a transition to a different form of interaction on the part of the family. (Therefore, by the way, in a crisis situation, advice like "don't swear", "well, you can't just quarrel" - do not work). Solving a crisis situation is a new form of interaction, relationships, roles in the family. And the successful passage of the crisis makes the family stronger and able to find solutions in other difficult situations.

So how does a family crisis manifest itself? The psychological distance between family members is changing. In addition, both in the direction of distance from each other, and in the direction of ultimate closeness - this is the name of the union in which each person does not see himself as a separate person. Family roles begin to be distributed unevenly - someone

may be overly dominant, or some family members take on family roles and responsibilities, and someone is forcibly or deliberately removed. The values, traditions, rituals and rules that have developed in the family are violated, difficulties arise in creating new ones, the expectations of family members are not supported or do not correspond to reality. Values, traditions, rituals, rules that have developed in the family will be violated, there will be difficulties in creating new ones. The expectations of family members are not supported or do not correspond to reality, the family becomes rigid, there is no flexibility, problems that arise are solved in some standard way.

CONCLUSION: Even before the creation of a family, these are two people living separately from each other - in parental families or on their own. Then they meet, become a couple and begin to live together. At the next stage, a child appears and the couple becomes parents. There may be more children, the family is growing. There may be grandchildren. Gradually, the time comes for each of the spouses to grow up and die. If the family does not get used to the new conditions during the passage of any stage, cannot solve new problems, it will face difficulties and go through a very difficult period. forgive. This is called a regulatory crisis. Of course, each transitional stage does not guarantee the emergence of a crisis situation in the family. But in these moments, the family is most vulnerable. There are also such crisis situations, which are almost impossible to predict. They are caused by external events - loss of a job or home, infidelity, serious illness of one of the spouses, marriage between relatives, divorce, marital status participant's death. Such situations are very difficult, they often lead to serious personality crises of family members.

In this article, several views are put forward on the personal activity of a gifted child, as well as the formation and implementation of individual talent on the basis of which the psychological mechanisms of self-development of the lying person are important.

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.

Uzbekistan has a rich experience of political life, features of political consciousness and develops in unique and difficult conditions. Thus, it turned out that it is wrong to copy a simple copy of the political experience of the Western world.

The basis of education is the family environment. The child grows by imitating what he sees at home. In the family, the father should be noble, open, calm, thoughtful and a little more political, and the mother should be kind, compassionate, not cursing her children in vain, and gentle. Parents also have a responsibility to raise our children with healthy beliefs and physical strength. Sacred space is a place of spirituality that ensures the development of national and universal values, preserves the continuity of the nation, and gives birth to a spiritually and physically perfect generation into the world. Thus, the family is the main basis for the formation of a person as a person, finding his place in life, gaining respect in the country. The family is the center of education, which ensures the continuity of the eternity of life, preserves our sacred traditions, and at the same time has a direct impact on how future generations become people.

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